

Center and Centroid of graphson Dominating Sets

D MADHUSUDANA REDDY, R SIVA GOPAL, B VENKATA RAMANA

ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ^{1,2,3}

madhuskd@gmail.com, sivagopal222@gmail.com, bvramana.bv@gmail.com

Department of mathematics,

Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,

N.H 44, Hampapuram, Raphthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722D

Abstract—Let S be a minimum dominating set of a connected undirected graph $G = (V, E)$. In this paper we study and analyze center and centroid of graphson dominating sets.

The S -distance of a vertex u is defined by $d_S(u) = \sum_{v \in S} d(u, v)$. A vertex u of G is said to be a S -centroid vertex if it minimizes $d_S(u) = \sum_{v \in S} d(u, v)$. The S -centroid graph of

G is the graph induced by the set of all S -centroid vertices and is denoted by $C_S(G)$. The S -eccentricity of a vertex u is defined by $e_S(u) = \max\{d(u, v) : v \in S\}$. From this we can define the S -radius of G as $rad_S(G) = \min\{e_S(u) : u \in V(G)\}$ and the S -diameter of G as $diam_S(G) = \max\{e_S(u) : u \in V(G)\}$. Now the vertex u is a S -central vertex if $e_S(u) =$

$rad_S(G)$, and the S -center $C_S(G)$ is the graph induced by the set of all S -central vertices. An edge e of G is said to be a S -centroid edge if it minimizes $d_S(e) = \sum_{v \in S} d(e, v)$. The S -centroid graph of G with respect to edge-to-

vertex distance is the graph induced by the set of all S -centroid edges and is denoted by $C_{2_S}(G)$. The S -eccentricity of an edge e is defined by $e_{2_S}(e) = \max\{d(e, v) : v \in S\}$. From this we can define the S -radius of G as $rad_{2_S}(G) = \min\{e_{2_S}(e) : e \in E(G)\}$ and the

S -diameter of G as $d_{2_S}(G) = \max\{e_{2_S}(e) : e \in E(G)\}$. Now the vertex u is a S -central edge if $e_{2_S}(e) = rad_S(G)$, and the

S -center $C_{2_S}(G)$ with respect to edge-to-vertex distance is the graph induced by the set of all S -central edges.

Keywords— S -status, S -centroid, S -center, graphs, dominating set, eccentricities, centre

Keywords— S -status, S -centroid, S -center, graphs, dominating set, eccentricities, centre

INTRODUCTION

Centrality is one of the fundamental notions which have established close connection between graph theory and various other areas like social networks. The main objective of any facility location problem is to identify the location for the facility for community or a set of customers such that the

distance between the location and the community or customers is minimized.

The graph center problem is interesting from both a structural and the algorithmic point of view. P. J. Slater generalized the concept of center of a graph to center of a profile of the vertex set of the graph. Graphs are often used to model such things as street networks and communication networks, and many mathematical problems have arisen from different instances of the question of what is an optimal location for a facility in a graph. In the almost cases the type of facility to be established is one for which a "central" location is optimal. The study of minimizing the total distance from the facility to certain important sites is the concept, S -distance.

We consider only finite simple undirected connected graphs. For a graph G , V denotes the vertex set and E denotes the edge set.

In 1964, Hakimi [4] considered the facility location problems as vertex-to-vertex distance in graphs. For any two vertices u and v in a connected graph G , the distance $d(u, v)$ is the length of a shortest $u-v$ path in G . For a vertex v in G , the eccentricity $e(v)$ of v is the distance between v and a vertex farthest from v in G . The minimum eccentricity among the vertices of G is its radius and the maximum eccentricity is its diameter, denoted by $rad(G)$ and $diam(G)$ respectively. A vertex v in G is a central vertex if $e(v) = rad(G)$ and the subgraph induced by the central vertices of G is the center $Cen(G)$ or $C(G)$ of G .

In 2010, Santhakumaran [7] introduced the facility location problem as edge-to-vertex distance in graphs as

follows: For an edge e and a vertex v in a connected graph G , the edge-to-vertex distance is defined by $d(e, v) = \min\{d(u, v) : u \text{ is any end vertex of } e\}$. The edge-to-vertex eccentricity is defined by $e_2(e) = \max\{d(e, v) : v \in V\}$. A vertex v of G such that $e_2(e) = d(e, v)$ is called an edge-to-vertex eccentric vertex of e . The edge-to-

vertex radius r_2 of G is defined by $r_2 = \min\{e_2(e) : e \in E\}$ and the edge-to-vertex diameter d_2 of G is defined by $d_2 = \max\{e_2(e) : e \in E\}$. An edge e for which $e_2(e)$ is minimum is called an edge-to-vertex central edge of G and the set of all edge-to-vertex central edges of G is the edge-to-vertex center $C_2(G)$ of G . For a set S of vertices, let the closed interval $I[S]$ of S be the union of the closed intervals $I[v,w]$ over all the pairs of vertices v and w in S . For a set S of edges, let the closed interval $I_2[S]$ of S be the union of the closed intervals $I[e,f]$ over all the pairs of edges e and f whose end points belongs to V . A set $S \subseteq V(G)$ is a dominating set of G if every vertex in $V(G)$ is either belongs to S or is adjacent to a vertex of S . The minimum dominating set or γ -set is a dominating set of minimum cardinality.

In this paper we consider the set S as the minimum dominating set.

I. S-CENTERS AND S-CENTROID ON γ -SETS WITH RESPECT TO VERTEX-TO-VERTEX DISTANCE

In this section we construct some basic theorems on S -Center and S -Centroid on minimum dominating sets with respect to vertex-to-vertex distance. Let $G=(V,E)$ be a graph and S be any subset of the vertex set V . Then the S -distance of a vertex u is defined by $d_S(u) = \sum_{v \in S} d(u,v)$. A vertex u of G is said to be a S -centroid vertex if it minimize $d_S(u) = \sum_{v \in S} d(u,v)$. The S -centroid graph of G is the graph induced by the set of all S -centroid vertices and is denoted by $C_\gamma(G)$.

The S -eccentricity of a vertex u is defined by $e_S(u) = \max\{d(u,v) : v \in S\}$. From this we can define the

S -radius of G as $rad_S(G) = \min\{e_S(u) : u \in V(G)\}$ and the S -diameter of G as $diam_S(G) = \max\{e_S(u) : u \in V(G)\}$. Now the vertex v is a S -central vertex if $e_S(u) = rad_S(G)$, and the S -center $C_S(G)$ is the graph induced by the set of all S -central vertices. In the following graph, we find S -centroid and S -center with respect to vertex-to-vertex distance.

Figure 1. A graph G

In this graph, the minimum dominating set is $S = \{v_1, v_5\}$. Here $d_S(v_1) = 3, d_S(v_2) = 3, d_S(v_3) = 3, d_S(v_4) = 3, d_S(v_5) = 3, d_S(v_6) = 5, d_S(v_7) = 5$ and also the set of all S -centroid vertices is $\{v_1, v_2, v_3, v_4, v_5\}$. Here, $e_S(v_1) = \max\{d(v_1, v_1), d(v_1, v_5)\} = 3, e_S(v_2) = \max\{d(v_2, v_1), d(v_2, v_5)\} = 2, e_S(v_3) = \max\{d(v_3, v_1), d(v_3, v_5)\} = 2, e_S(v_4) = \max\{d(v_4, v_1), d(v_4, v_5)\} = 2$ and so on.

Figure 2. The S -centroid of the graph shown in Figure 1

Hence $rad_S(G) = 2$, and so the set of all S -central vertices is $\{v_2, v_3, v_4\}$. From figure 1 we can construct the S -centroid and S -center.

Figure 3. The S-center of the graph G represented in Figure 1

Theorem 2.1

Let S be a set of a connected graph G . Then $rad_S(G) \leq rad(G)$.

Proof:

Let $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\}$ be the vertex set of G and let $S = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k\}$ be a subset of G , ($k \leq n$). Now $rad_S(G) = \min\{e_S(v_1), e_S(v_2), e_S(v_3), \dots, e_S(v_n), v_i \in V(G), i = 1 \text{ to } n\}$. We have to prove $rad_S(G) \leq rad(G)$. Let $rad(G) = m$ and let u be a central vertex of G . Then $e(u) = d(u, w) = m$ where w is the eccentric vertex of u . Now we analyze the location of the vertex w in two cases.

case (i): Suppose $w \in S$, then clearly $rad_S(G) = rad(G)$.

case (ii): Suppose $w \notin S$, then S contains the vertices v_i such that $d(u, v_i) < m \forall i = 1 \text{ to } m$.

Therefore, $rad_S(G) \leq rad(G)$.

Theorem 2.2

Let S be a set of a connected graph G . Then $diam_S(G) \leq diam(G)$.

Remark 2.3

If $S = \{v\}$, then $rad_S(G) = 0$ and $C_S(G) = \{v\}$. From this we conclude the property that $rad_S(G) \leq diam_S(G) \leq 2rad_S(G)$ is not hold.

Theorem 2.4

Let S be a minimum dominating set of a connected graph G . Then the S-center is a subset of $I[S]$.

Proof:

Let S be a minimum dominating set of a connected graph G , say $S = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_k\}$. Let v be a S-central

vertex. Then we have to show that v belongs to $I[S]$. Suppose to the contrary that we take v is not in $I[S]$. We have to show that v is not a S-central vertex. Then v is dominated by a vertex u_i ($1 \leq i \leq k$) of S . Then $e_S(v) = \max\{d(v, u_i) : u_i \in S\}$ is not minimum. Therefore v is not a S-central vertex. Hence the set of all S-central vertices is a subset of $I[S]$.

Corollary 2.5

T

he S-

center $C_S(G)$

is contained in the Steiner tree of S .

Remark 2.6

Let S be a minimum dominating set of a connected graph G . Then the central vertices and the set of all S-central vertices need not be same.

Theorem 2.7

The S-center of any connected graph G lies within a block.

Proof:

Suppose the S-center $C_S(G)$ of a connected graph lies in more than one block. Then G contains a cut vertex v such that $G-v$ has components G_1 and G_2 , each of which contains a S-central vertex of G . Let u be a S-eccentric vertex of v and let P be a $u-v$ path of length $e_S(v)$. Then v contains no vertex from at least one of G_1 and G_2 , say G_1 . Let w be a S-central vertex of G_1 and P' be a $w-v$ geodesic in G . Suppose u has another S-eccentric vertex x , then $e_S(u) = d(u, w) = m$ and $e_S(u) = d(u, x) = m$. Assume that $w \in S$ and $x \notin S$ then $rad_S(G) = rad(G)$.

Then $e_S(w) \geq d(w, v) + d(v, u) \geq 1 + e_S(v)$ which is a contradiction to w is a S-central vertex. Then all the S-central vertices must lie in a single block.

Theorem 2.8

■

Proof: In a tree T , every S -central vertex is a central vertex.

Let u be a S -central vertex. We have $e(u) = \text{Grad}(T) \Rightarrow e(u) > \text{rad}(T)$. We take $e(u) = \text{rad}(T) + 1$. Therefore there exists an eccentric vertex $v \in V$ for u , $e(u) = d(u, v) = \text{rad}(T) + 1$. Since u is a S -central vertex, $e_S(u) = \text{rad}_S(T)$, there exists a S -eccentric vertex $w \in S$ for u . That is, $d(u, w) = e_S(u) = \text{rad}_S(T)$. Hence $v \in S$ or $v \notin S$.
 case(i): Suppose that $v \in S$. Since v is a farthest vertex to u in V , v is the farthest vertex to u in S , $d(u, v) = e_S(u) = \text{rad}_S(T)$. $\text{rad}(T) + 1 = e_S(u) = \text{rad}_S(T)$. Hence $\text{rad}(T) + 1 = \text{rad}_S(T)$ which implies $\text{rad}(T) < \text{rad}_S(T)$ which is a contradiction to u is a S -central vertex. Hence u is a central vertex.
 case(ii): Suppose $v \notin S$. Since S is a γ -set, v is dominated by S .
 Proof:

u . Since u is a S -central vertex, it is clear that v is an end vertex. Since S is a γ -set, v is dominated by at least one vertex, say $x \in S$. Hence we have $d(v, x) = 1$. Since v is the farthest vertex to u , x lies between u and v . That is, $d(u, v) = d(u, x) + d(x, v)$ which implies that $d(u, x) = \text{rad}_S(T)$. Therefore, $\text{rad}(T) = \text{rad}_S(T) + 1$. Hence, $\text{rad}_S(T) = \text{rad}(T) - 1$.

Theorem 2.10

In a tree T , every central vertex is a S -central vertex.

Proof:

Let u be a central vertex. Now u is a central vertex, there exists a S -eccentric vertex v in V such that $d(u, v) = e(u) = \text{rad}(T)$. We have to show that u is a S -central vertex. Hence there are two cases, $v \in S$ or $v \notin S$.
 ■

II. S -CENTER AND S -CENTROID ON γ -SETS WITH RESPECT TO EDGE-TO-VERTEX DISTANCE

In this section we construct some basic theorems on S -Center and S -Centroid on minimum dominating sets with respect to edge-to-vertex distance. The S -distance of an edge e is defined by $d_S(e) = \sum_{v \in S} d(e, v)$. An edge e of G is said to be a S -centroid edge if it minimizes $d_S(e) = \sum_{v \in S} d(e, v)$.

Figure 3. A graph

The S -centroid graph of G with respect to edge-to-vertex distance is the graph induced by the set of all S -centroid edges and is denoted by $C_{2,\gamma}(G)$. The S -eccentricity of an edge e is defined by $e_{2,\gamma}(e) = \max\{d(e, v) : v \in S\}$. From

to show that u is a central vertex. Suppose u is not a central vertex. That

at least one vertex say $x \in S$. Hence we have $d(v, x) = 1$. Since v is the farthest vertex to u , x lies between u and v , i.e., $d(u, v) = d(u, x) + d(x, v)$ which implies $\text{rad}(T) + 1 = d(u, x) + d(x, v)$. Therefore, $d(u, x) = \text{rad}(T)$. Since $x \in S$, x is the farthest vertex to u in S , $d(u, x) = \text{rad}_S(T)$. Therefore we get, $\text{rad}_S(T) = \text{rad}(T)$ which is a contradiction to u is a S -central vertex. In both the cases on v there are contradictions on u is a S -central vertex. Hence u is a central vertex.

For a tree T , $\text{rad}_S(T) = \text{rad}(T) - 1$ if S contains no end vertices.

Let u be a central vertex in T . It implies that $\text{rad}(T) = d(u, v) = e(u)$, where v is an eccentric vertex for $v \notin S$.

case(i): Suppose $v \in S$. Since v is a farthest vertex to u , v is the farthest vertex to u in S , $d(u, v) = e_S(u) = \text{rad}_S(T)$. Hence u is a S -central vertex.

case(ii): Suppose $v \notin S$. Since S is a γ -set, v is dominated by at least one vertex say $x \in S$. Hence $d(v, x) = 1$ and so x is the farthest vertex to u and is in S and so $d(u, x) = e_S(u)$. Since v is the farthest vertex to u and $v \notin S$, $d(u, x) = e_S(u)$. Therefore, $d(u, x) = \text{rad}(T)$. Since $x \in S$, x is the farthest vertex to u in S , $d(u, x) = \text{rad}_S(T)$. Therefore, $\text{rad}_S(T) = \text{rad}(T)$, which is a contradiction to u is a S -central vertex. In both the cases there are contradictions on u is a S -central vertex and so u is a central vertex.

this we can define the S -radius of G as $r_{2_s}(G) = \min\{e_{2_s}(e):e \in E(G)\}$ and the S -diameter of G as $d_{2_s}(G) = \max\{e_{2_s}(e):e \in E(G)\}$. Now the vertex v is a S -central edge if $e_{2_s}(e) = rad_s(G)$, and the S -center $C_{2_s}(G)$ with respect to edge - to- vertex distance is the graph induced by the set of all S -central edges.

In the above graph, we find S -centroid and S -center with respect to edge-to-vertex distance.

Let us assume $e_1 = v_1v_2, e_2 = v_1v_3, e_3 = v_2v_4, e_4 = v_3v_4, e_5 = v_4v_5, e_6 = v_5v_6, e_7 = v_5v_7$. In this graph the minimum dominating set is $S = \{v_1, v_5\}$. Here $d_s(e_1) = 0 + 2 = 2, d_s(e_2) = 0 + 2 = 2, d_s(e_3) = 1 + 1 = 2, d_s(e_4) = 1 + 1 = 2, d_s(e_5) = 2 + 0 = 2, d_s(e_6) = 3 + 0 = 3, d_s(e_7) = 3 + 0 = 3$ and also the set of all S -centroid edges is $\{e_1, e_2, e_3, e_4, e_5\}$.

v_2

$C_{2_\gamma}(G)$:

v_3

Figure 4. The S -centroid with respect to edge-to-vertex distance of the graph G represented in Figure 3

Here, $e_{2_s}(e_1) = \max\{d(e_1, v_1), d(e_1, v_5)\} = 2, e_{2_s}(e_2) = \max\{d(e_2, v_1), d(e_2, v_5)\} = 2, e_{2_s}(e_3) = \max\{d(e_3, v_1), d(e_3, v_5)\} = 2, e_{2_s}(e_4) = \max\{d(e_4, v_1), d(e_4, v_5)\} = 1, e_{2_s}(e_5) = \max\{d(e_5, v_1), d(e_5, v_5)\} = 3, e_{2_s}(e_6) = \max\{d(e_6, v_1), d(e_6, v_5)\} = 3, e_{2_s}(e_7) = \max\{d(e_7, v_1), d(e_7, v_5)\} = 3$. Hence, $r_{2_s}(G) = 1$, and so the S -center is $C_{2_s}(G) = \{e_4\}$.

$C_{2_s}(G)$:

v_3

Figure 5. The S -center with respect to edge-to-vertex distance of the graph G represented in Figure 3

We know that the S -eccentricity of a edge e is defined by $e_{2_s}(e) = \max\{d(e, v):v \in S\}$. From this we can define the S -radius as $r_{2_s}(G) = \min\{e_{2_s}(e):e \in E(G)\}$ and the S -diameter as $d_{2_s}(G) = \max\{e_{2_s}(e):e \in E(G)\}$.

Now v is a S -central edge if $e_{2_s}(e) = r_{2_s}(G)$ and the S -center $C_{2_s}(G)$ is the set of all S -central edges.

In the Figure 2, for the γ -Set $S = \{v_1, v_5\}$, $r_{2_s}(G) = 1$ and $d_{2_s}(G) = 3$.

Theorem 3.1

Let S be a set of a connected graph G . Then $r_{2_s}(G) \leq r_2(G)$.

Proof.

Let $E(G) = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n\}$ be the vertex set of G and let $S = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_k\}$ be a γ -set of G , ($k \leq n$).

Now $r_{2_s}(G) = \min\{e_{2_s}(e_1), e_{2_s}(e_2), e_{2_s}(e_3), \dots, e_{2_s}(e_n), e_i \in E(G), i = 1 \text{ to } n\}$. We have to prove that $r_{2_s}(G) \leq r_2(G)$. Let $r_2(G) = m$ and let w be a central vertex of G . Then $e_2(w) = d(w, v) = m$ where w is the eccentric vertex of e . Now we analyze the location of the vertex w into two cases.

case (i). Suppose that $w \in S$, then clearly $r_{2_s}(G) = r_2(G)$.

case (ii). Suppose that $w \notin S$, then S contains the vertices v_i such that $d(e, v_i) < m$ for every $i = 1$ to m . Hence $r_{2_s}(G) < r_2(G)$. Therefore, $r_{2_s}(G) \leq r_2(G)$. ■

Theorem 3.2

Let S be a set of a connected graph G . Then $d_{2_s}(G) \leq d_2(G)$.

Proof.

The proof is similar to the proof of Theorem 2.3. ■

Remark 3.3

Let S be a minimum dominating set of a connected graph G . Then the central edges and the set of all S -central edges need not be same.

Theorem 3.4

In a tree T , every S -central edge is a central edge.

Proof.

Let e be a S -central edge. We have to show that e is a central edge. Suppose e is not a central edge. i.e., $e_{2_s}(e) > r_2(T) \Rightarrow e_{2_s}(e) > r_2(T)$. We take $e_{2_s}(e) = r_2(T) + 1$. Therefore there exists an eccentric vertex $v \in V$ for e , $e_{2_s}(e) = d(e, v) = r_2(T) + 1$. Since e is a S -central edge, $e_{2_s}(e) = r_{2_s}(T)$, there exists a S -eccentric vertex $w \in S$ for e . That is, $d(e, w) = e_{2_s}(e) = r_{2_s}(T)$. Hence $v \in S$ or $v \notin S$.

Case (i): Suppose $v \in S$. Since v is a farthest vertex to e in V , v is the farthest vertex to e in S , $d(e, v) = e_{2_s}(e) = r_{2_s}(T) \cdot r_2(T) + 1 = e_{2_s}(e) = r_{2_s}(T)$. Hence $r_2(T) + 1 = r_{2_s}(T)$ which implies $r_2(T) < r_{2_s}(T)$ which is a contradiction to e is a S -central edge. Hence e is a central edge.

Case (ii): Suppose $v \notin S$. Since S is a γ -set, v is dominated by at least one vertex $x \in S$. Hence we have $d(v, x) = 1$. Since v is the farthest vertex to e , x lies between e and v . That is, $d(e, v) = d(e, x) + d(x, v)$ which implies $r_2(T) + 1 = d(e, x) + 1$. Therefore, $d(e, x) = r_2(T)$. Since $x \in S$, x is the farthest vertex to e in S , $d(e, x) = r_{2_s}(T)$. Therefore we get, $r_{2_s}(T) = r_2(T)$ which is a contradiction to e is a S -central edge. In both the cases on v there are contradictions on e is a S -central edge. Hence, e is a central edge. ■

CONCLUSION

Centre and centroid are two crucial emergency locations that are examined in this research. In contrast to the usual practice of defining them using vertices, they are defined here by fixing a preponderant set of graphs. Additionally, they are described in relation to edges. In addition, we define vertex to edge and edges to edge lengths and verify and list their qualities.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Esther Jennings., Distributed Algorithms for Finding Central Paths in Tree Networks, The Computer Journal, Vol 42, No 7, Pages 609-612 (1999).
- [2] F. Buckley and F. Harary, Distance in Graphs, Addison-Wesley, Reading, MA (1990).
- [3] G. Chartrand and P. Zhang., Introduction to Graph Theory, Tata McGraw Hill, Publishing Company Limited, New Delhi (2006).
- [4] S.L. Hakimi, Optimum location of switching centers and absolute centers and medians of a graph, Operations Research, 12 (1964).
- [5] Peter J. Slater., Center to Centers in Graphs, Journal of Graph Theory, Vol 2, Pages 209-222 (1978).
- [6] Ram Kumar. R, Kannan Balakrishnan, Manoj Changanat, A. Sree Kumar, Prasanth G. Narasimha-Shenoi., On The Center Sets and Center Numbers of Some graph Classes, eprint arXIV:1312.3182[cs.DM] 11 Dec 2013.

- [7] San Aye and Min Aung., n-Centrum and Steiner n-Center of a Tree, AU Journal of Technology, Vol 5, No. 4 (2002), Pages 199-202.
- [8] A.P. Santhakumaran, Center of a graph with respect to edges, SCIENTIA Series A: Mathematical Sciences, 19 (2010), 13-23.